

1 **Title:** Meta-analysis reveals that the effects of precipitation change on soil and litter fauna in
2 forests depend on body size

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4 **Running title:** Precipitation change impacts on soil fauna

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32 **Abstract**

33 Anthropogenic climate change is altering precipitation regimes at a global scale. While
34 precipitation changes have been linked to changes in the abundance and diversity of soil
35 and litter invertebrate fauna in forests, general trends have remained elusive due to mixed
36 results from primary studies. We used a meta-analysis based on 430 comparisons from 38
37 primary studies to address associated knowledge gaps, (i) quantifying impacts of
38 precipitation change on forest soil and litter fauna abundance and diversity, (ii) exploring
39 reasons for variation in impacts, and (iii) examining biases affecting the realism and
40 accuracy of experimental studies. Precipitation reductions led to a decrease of 39% in soil
41 and litter fauna abundance, with a 35% increase in abundance under precipitation increases,
42 while diversity impacts were smaller. A statistical model containing an interaction between
43 body size and the magnitude of precipitation change showed that mesofauna (e.g. mites,
44 collembola) responded most to changes in precipitation. Changes in taxonomic richness
45 were related solely to the magnitude of precipitation change. Our results suggest that body
46 size is related to the ability of a taxon to survive under drought conditions, or to benefit from
47 high precipitation. We also found that most experiments manipulated precipitation in a way
48 that aligns better with predicted extreme climatic events than with predicted average annual
49 changes in precipitation and that the experimental plots used in experiments were likely too
50 small to accurately capture changes for mobile taxa. The relationship between body size and
51 response to precipitation found here has far-reaching implications for our ability to predict
52 future responses of soil biodiversity to climate change and will help to produce more realistic
53 mechanistic soil models which aim to simulate the responses of soils to global change.

54 **Keywords:** Precipitation change; drought; Soil fauna; meta-analysis; evidence synthesis;
55 climate change

56

57 **Introduction**

58 Anthropogenic climate change is altering global precipitation patterns (Seager et al., 2018)
59 and increasing the frequency and severity of extreme drought and precipitation events (Sun
60 et al., 2007). Understanding the consequences of precipitation changes is particularly vital
61 for forests, given their critical roles in the global carbon cycle (Walker et al., 2021) and in
62 supporting global biodiversity (Benton et al., 2022). Impacts of precipitation changes on
63 forests include increased tree mortality (Anderegg et al., 2019) and consequent increases in
64 CO₂ emissions (Doughty et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2018), and mixed effects on aboveground
65 forest biodiversity (Fleming et al., 2021). However, the effects of disturbances on the
66 biodiversity of soil and litter invertebrate fauna in forests, remains poorly known (Pressler et
67 al., 2019; Winding et al., 2020) despite its importance in regulating organic matter
68 decomposition, nutrient cycling, and plant health among other ecosystem functions (Handa
69 et al., 2014; Nielsen et al., 2015).

70 Since soil moisture is a key limiting factor to the fitness and behaviour of many soil
71 and litter fauna, precipitation changes may threaten the processes to which they contribute
72 (Coyle et al., 2017). Precipitation changes and associated changes in soil moisture and
73 distribution of water within the soil matrix can alter the movement of microfauna such as
74 nematodes, and therefore their access to food sources, or the humidity in pores which
75 represent the habitat of mesofauna such as Collembola (Coyle et al., 2017; Deckmyn et al.,
76 2020). These changes can alter reproduction and mortality of a wide range of soil and litter
77 fauna (Kardol et al., 2011; Singh et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2022). For example, extreme
78 drought conditions can increase mortality for taxa such as Collembola (Wang et al., 2022)
79 and Enchytraeidae (Maraldo et al., 2009). Nonetheless, while some studies have reported
80 biodiversity losses as a result of precipitation reduction (Aupic-Samain, Santonja, et al.,
81 2021; Chikoski et al., 2006; Lindberg et al., 2002; Santonja et al., 2017) others have reported
82 increases (Homet et al., 2021; Lensing et al., 2005), with similarly mixed results for studies

83 of precipitation increases (Chikoski et al., 2006; Frew et al., 2013; Landesman et al., 2011)
84 making generalisation challenging.

85 One obvious reason for heterogeneity among studies of soil faunal responses to
86 precipitation change is the magnitude of the precipitation change itself. Most studies of
87 precipitation change represent manipulative experiments often using rain exclusion devices
88 for reduction treatments or irrigation for precipitation increases, with ambient conditions used
89 as a control. Meta-analyses have failed to find a consistent relationship between the
90 magnitude of precipitation changes and changes in either the abundance or taxonomic
91 richness of soil fauna (Peng et al., 2022). This could in part reflect diverging responses in
92 taxonomic groups to precipitation changes (Coyle et al., 2017). Functional traits,
93 morphological, physiological or phenological features measurable at the individual level
94 (Violle et al., 2007), might offer a tractable way to disentangle some of these differences.

95 There are many traits that could influence soil faunal responses to precipitation
96 change. Here we focus on three. First, taxa that inhabit the litter layer are likely to be more
97 exposed to extreme fluctuations in moisture, and thus to respond more strongly than taxa
98 inhabiting deeper, more buffered soil horizons (Fraser et al., 2012). Second, the presence of
99 an exoskeleton and a cuticle layer that helps to reduce water loss and may hence render
100 arthropods less prone to desiccation than soft-bodied annelids such as Enchytraeidae
101 (Evans, 2008; Singh et al., 2019). Third, body size relates to microhabitat preferences and
102 therefore dependence on water availability. For example, microfauna, such as nematodes,
103 inhabit water films, so may be particularly vulnerable as they are essentially aquatic
104 organisms (Vandegheuchte et al., 2015), mesofauna, such as Collembola, are sensitive to
105 changes in soil moisture because they are confined to existing air-filled pore spaces (Wang
106 et al., 2022) while macrofauna can create their own pore spaces (Lavelle et al., 2002) and
107 are more capable of avoidant behaviour such as burrowing to deeper depths (Gerard, 1967).
108 Therefore, increasing body size likely yields greater resistance to changes in precipitation.

109 In addition to functional traits, the characteristics of forest ecosystems could also
110 influence the responses of soil and litter fauna to precipitation changes. For example, in

111 relatively arid regions that have regularly been exposed to drought conditions in the past, soil
112 and litter fauna communities will have been subject to environmental filtering, which selects
113 for combinations of functional traits that govern species' ability to persist in the local
114 environment (Balmford, 1996; Kraft et al., 2015). This means that we might expect greater
115 reductions in the abundance of soil and litter fauna in humid forests following precipitation
116 reductions than in relatively arid forests. Equally, we might expect greater increases in
117 abundance in arid forests following precipitation increases. Integrating information on
118 functional traits and ecosystem characteristics into research syntheses should allow for a
119 mechanistic understanding as to why soil faunal responses to precipitation are
120 heterogeneous.

121 Alongside a lack of understanding of between-study variability, it is also unclear how
122 study design impacts study results. Meta-research in ecology has shown that differences in
123 experimental and sampling designs can have large impacts on the accuracy of estimates of
124 biodiversity change (Christie et al., 2019, 2020; Spake et al., 2021). But methodological
125 robustness is rarely assessed in ecological meta-analyses (Pullin et al., 2022). As well as
126 methodological robustness, it is also unclear if experimental studies employ realistic future
127 precipitation scenarios. This is a particularly serious issue, given existing concerns about the
128 use of unrealistic precipitation manipulations in global change experiments which may result
129 in under- or over- estimations of impact (Korell et al., 2020; Kröel-Dulay et al., 2022).

130 To address these knowledge gaps, we carried out the first meta-analysis of the effects
131 of precipitation changes on soil and litter fauna in forests. In this study, we address three
132 questions: (1) What are the impacts of precipitation changes on the abundance and diversity
133 of forest soil and litter invertebrate fauna? (2) What are the major determinants of the impacts
134 of precipitation changes on abundance and diversity? (3) What are the major biases in studies
135 of the impacts of precipitation change on forest soil and litter invertebrate fauna?

136 For question 1, we hypothesised that precipitation reductions cause declines in the
137 abundance and diversity of soil and litter fauna, whereas additional precipitation causes an
138 increase in abundance and diversity (H1, Figure 1a). For question 2, we tested five

139 hypotheses: (i) an increased magnitude of changes in precipitation amplifies changes in
140 abundance and diversity (H2, Figure 1b); (ii) the effect of precipitation magnitude is further
141 amplified for organisms found in litter compared to soil dwellers (H3, Figure 1c), (iii) for
142 organisms without an exoskeleton compared to those with an exoskeleton (H4, Figure 1d),
143 (iv) for organisms with smaller body sizes (H5, Figure 1e), (v) or that organisms in moist forests
144 are more sensitive to reductions in precipitation, while organisms in drier forests are sensitive
145 to increases in precipitation (H6, Figure 1f). There were no hypotheses for question 3.

146

147 **Materials and Methods**

148 **Searches and screening**

149 This study focuses on the impacts of precipitation changes on forest soil and litter
150 invertebrate fauna in field settings. We formally defined these as PECOS elements (Table 1,
151 Grames et al., 2019). More precise definitions of these elements can be found in the
152 Supplementary methods. This study follows guidelines for synthesis in environmental
153 management (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence, 2018). We chose to focus on
154 precipitation change because although there are numerous primary studies investigating its
155 impact there is currently a lack of robust synthesis. We did not focus on the impacts of other
156 important global change drivers such as temperature change due to existing meta-analyses
157 on this topic (Goncharov et al., 2023; Peng et al., 2022).

158 As part of a previous systematic map (Martin et al., 2021), we screened a large
159 number of papers to identify those that assessed the impact of natural disturbances on soil
160 and litter invertebrate fauna in forests (see Supplementary methods for a summary of
161 systematic map methods). From the systematic map we identified 320 articles that related to
162 impacts of natural disturbances. On the 22nd of February 2024, we updated our search by
163 searching in three bibliographic platforms (Web of Science, Scopus, and Open Access
164 Theses and Dissertations) to find studies on the impact of precipitation changes on soil and

165 litter invertebrate fauna in forests published after our initial systematic map searches. Since
166 different bibliographic platforms have different rules for the formatting of searches, we
167 developed platform-specific searches (see Tables S2 and S3). By searching for unpublished
168 grey literature as well as published, peer-reviewed literature, we aimed to minimise the risk
169 of publication bias which could lead to inaccurate estimates of disturbance impacts (Konno &
170 Pullin, 2020). In addition to formal searches, we contacted expert researchers to help identify
171 potentially relevant studies.

172 Once searches were complete, we downloaded all references found as .bib or .ris
173 files and used the R package *synthesisr* to remove duplicate articles (Westgate & Grames,
174 2020). The *bibfix* package (Haddaway et al., 2021) was used to repair bibliographic files
175 with incomplete data. Files were then uploaded to *sysrev* (Bozada et al., 2021) - an online
176 tool that allows for screening and data extraction by review teams (see Martin, 2021). Article
177 titles and abstracts were screened for relevance, and articles that met inclusion criteria were
178 retained and their full text reviewed. To meet our eligibility criteria studies needed to: (1)
179 Relate to soil and litter fauna in forests; (2) Address the impact of changes in precipitation;
180 (3) Be field-based (i.e. not be carried out in greenhouses or mesocosms); (4) Quantitatively
181 assess soil fauna biomass, abundance, or diversity; (5) Have a comparison between sites
182 that vary in the intensity or frequency of the precipitation that they were exposed to; (6) Be
183 written in English; (7) Report measures of centrality (mean or median) for relevant litter or
184 soil fauna outcomes.

185 At the title and abstract screening stage, in order to be retained, articles needed to be
186 likely to meet criteria 1-3 and criterion 5. At the full-text stage criteria 1-7 needed to be met in
187 order for an article to be retained. At the full-text screening stage, we provided reasons for
188 the exclusion of all articles that did not meet our inclusion criteria in accordance with ROSES
189 guidelines (Haddaway et al., 2018; Figure S1). Despite being a multilingual team, we
190 focussed only on English-language literature because the inclusion of non-English language
191 literature would have made carrying out consistency checks between reviewers challenging.

192 We acknowledge that excluding literature written in non-English languages is a shortcoming
193 that may lead to biases (Amano et al., 2021; Konno et al., 2020).

194 To ensure consistency, a random sample of 10% of titles and abstracts were
195 screened by two team members, using our inclusion criteria. Any disagreements between
196 the two people were discussed, and eligibility criteria were revised where appropriate.
197 Cohen's Kappa scores were calculated to test the agreement between the two people
198 (Cohen, 1960). If Kappa scores were below 0.6, another 10% of titles and abstracts were
199 screened by the same two team members with the process repeated until Kappa scores
200 were >0.6. The same process was repeated for the full texts of publications that met
201 inclusion criteria. After screening of titles and abstracts, inter-reviewer agreement was 98.7%
202 and the Kappa score was 0.93. For full text screening agreement was 100% and the Kappa
203 score was 1.0. We found 1965 papers during our updated searches, 82 of which were
204 retained after screening of titles and abstracts, and 38 of which were used for critical
205 appraisal and data extraction. We used 430 comparisons between control and treatment
206 groups extracted from these studies. The screening process is summarised in more detail in
207 Figure S1.

208 **Critical appraisal**

209 Critical appraisal of studies to assess their methodological robustness is a vital part
210 of synthesis (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence, 2018). We did this by assessing the
211 following threats to the internal validity of a study based on Martin et al. (2020) (i) selection
212 bias: when selection of study sites leads to a result that is systematically different to the
213 target population; (ii) confounding: where systematic distortion of the effect of a treatment
214 caused by mixing of the treatment of interest with other disturbances (e.g. plots where
215 precipitation was manipulated were in plantations while control plots were in natural forests);
216 and (iii) performance bias, differences that occur due to knowledge by researchers about
217 treatment allocation. We therefore determined whether studies (i) consisted of both spatial
218 (i.e. comparisons between control and treatment groups) and temporal comparisons (i.e.

219 comparisons before and after a precipitation change), (ii) used randomisation to assign
220 treatment and control units, (iii) avoided confounding factors, and (iv) whether studies were
221 manipulative experiments that allow determination of causality. We assigned studies an
222 overall score of low, medium, or high validity depending on the fulfilment of a priori criteria
223 (see Table S5). These scores were later used in sensitivity analyses (see section on
224 Statistical analyses).

225

226 **Data extraction and coding**

227 We extracted data on the means, measures of variation, and sample sizes for each
228 relevant biodiversity measure both in control and treatment groups. When data for more than
229 one time period or site was presented in the same study we extracted all available data.
230 When variation around the mean was presented as standard errors we converted it to
231 standard deviation using the equation $SD = SE \times \sqrt{n}$ where SE refers to the standard error
232 and n refers to the sample size. Where data was presented in the form of figures we
233 extracted this using the R package *metadigitise* (Pick et al., 2019). In total 16% of studies
234 lacked data on variation and 14% lacked data on sample sizes and so to avoid problems
235 associated with excluding studies with missing data (Nakagawa & Freckleton, 2008) we
236 chose to impute these values using the method of Nakagawa et al. (2023). Using these data
237 we then calculated the log response ratio and its variance (Hedges et al., 1999) as
238 implemented by Nakagawa et al. (2023) for use as an effect size, which improves the
239 accuracy and precision of meta-analyses especially when sample sizes are small.

240 Regarding explanatory variables and contextual data, we extracted information on
241 the geographic location of studies, the perturbation type (precipitation reduction or
242 precipitation increase), the magnitude of precipitation change (% change compared to
243 control), the relevant taxonomic groups reported in a study, the size class of fauna
244 (microfauna, mesofauna, and macrofauna) based on Nielsen (2019), the kind of biodiversity
245 outcome measured (abundance, Shannon-Weiner diversity, or species richness), the

246 sampling design of the study based on Christie *et al.* (2019, 2020), the sampling method
247 (e.g. soil core, soil monolith, pitfall trap), the duration of study, the time after the beginning of
248 perturbation in precipitation at which fauna was sampled, and whether the fauna sampled
249 possessed an exoskeleton. Using study location data, we extracted information on site
250 aridity index (defined as ratio of mean annual precipitation over potential evapotranspiration)
251 using the data of Zomer *et al.* (2022). We turned aridity index values into a categorical
252 variable based on the recommended categories of Zomer *et al.* (2022), classifying sites with
253 an aridity index >0.65 as humid, and those <0.65 as arid.

254 **Statistical analyses**

255 We used multilevel meta-analytical models with inverse variance weighting as implemented
256 in the R package metafor (Viechtbauer, 2010). To examine the impacts of precipitation
257 reduction or increase on soil and litter fauna abundance, taxonomic richness, and Shannon-
258 Wiener diversity index (Figure 1a), we built models with no modifiers that included study and
259 site as nested random effects to account for the lack of independence between observations
260 from the same study and site (Nakagawa *et al.*, 2023). We chose not to combine the
261 different outcomes for diversity as doing so can blur responses and limit interpretability of
262 results (Liu *et al.*, 2023). We calculated the I^2 statistic to estimate the percentage of the total
263 variability in effect size values that was due to real heterogeneity. At this stage we also
264 performed two sensitivity analyses to test (i) the impact of removing studies that failed
265 Geary's test of normality (Nakagawa, Noble, *et al.*, 2023); (ii) the impact of removing studies
266 that we classified as having low validity in our critical appraisal.

267 To test our hypotheses about how precipitation change alters soil and litter fauna
268 biodiversity, we ran models that included the percentage change in annual precipitation
269 (Figure 1b). All of our other hypotheses involved interactions between changes in
270 precipitation and other variables, and so we also ran models including interactions with the
271 variables: (i) microhabitat (litter or soil, Figure 1c), (ii) presence of an exoskeleton (Figure
272 1d); (iii) body size of study taxon (Figure 1e), (iv) and aridity of the study forest (Figure 1f).

273 To account for the potential impacts of publication bias, we included a model parameter
274 representing the square root of the inverse of effective sample size (Nakagawa et al., 2021),
275 to test the impact of the small-study effect, in which smaller studies have different - often
276 larger - effect sizes when compared to larger studies. We also tested the potential of a
277 decline effect, in which the effect sizes reported by studies declines over time (Koricheva &
278 Kulinskaya, 2019; Nakagawa et al., 2021). Model selection was carried out using Akaike's
279 Information Criterion adjusted for small sample sizes (AICc) with models with a $\Delta AICc < 2$
280 considered to have similar support. We carried out model-averaging for models with a
281 $\Delta AICc < 2$ using the 'zero method' (Grueber et al., 2011) in the R package MuMIn (Barton,
282 2015) in order to produce model coefficients and associated statistics.

283 We assessed three different types of bias that may undermine the realism and
284 accuracy of estimates of biodiversity changes as a result of precipitation change. To
285 determine geographic biases, we plotted study locations on a map. We derived annual
286 precipitation and temperature data from the geographic coordinates of the sites and used the
287 R package plotbiomes to assess biases in the forest biomes that have been studied (Ştefan
288 & Levin, 2018). Next, we assessed the similarity of the precipitation changes simulated in
289 experiments to future projections of precipitation change in the same location. To do this we
290 calculated the change in precipitation imposed by experiments and used the R package
291 geodata (Hijmans et al., 2023) to compare this to projected values for the same location for
292 25 climate models (ACCESS-CM2, ACCESS-ESM1-5, AWI-CM-1-1-MR, BCC-CSM2-MR,
293 CanESM5, CanESM5-CanOE, CMCC-ESM2, CNRM-CM6-1, CNRM-CM6-1-HR, CNRM-
294 ESM2-1, EC-Earth3-Veg, EC-Earth3-Veg-LR, FIO-ESM-2-0, GISS-E2-1-G, GISS-E2-1-H,
295 HadGEM3-GC31-LL, INM-CM4-8, INM-CM5-0, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MIROC-ES2L, MIROC6,
296 MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MPI-ESM1-2-LR, MRI-ESM2-0, and UKESM1-0-LL) for the period 2041-
297 2060 for shared socio-economic pathway 245 - a medium carbon emissions scenario. We
298 used data from multiple climate models to account for potential differences between them.
299 We compared the precipitation rate for experiments to those projected to occur under our
300 selected emissions scenario for each experiment and model by calculating the log response

301 ratio between experimental and projected precipitation. We then ran linear mixed effects
302 models for each climate model with a random term for each study to assess whether
303 experiments that reduced or increased precipitation were similar in precipitation rates to
304 projected changes (as indicated by log response ratios not significantly different from zero).
305 Since results were similar for almost all climate models (see Figure S6), we summarised
306 them by calculating the median effect sizes and confidence intervals. Finally, given the
307 importance of spatial scale when estimating biodiversity changes (Chase & Knight, 2013;
308 Spake et al., 2021) we assessed the plot size at which treatments were applied in
309 experiments for fauna with different body sizes to identify where there may be a mismatch
310 between the mobility of taxa and the scale of experiments.

311

312 **Results**

313 **Description of data set**

314 Our dataset comprises 38 primary studies, representing 46 sites, and 430 effect sizes.
315 Almost half of sites were found in Europe (22 sites, 47%), followed by North America (10
316 sites, 22%), and Asia (7 sites, 15%), with relatively few in South America (4 sites, 8%) and
317 Oceania (3 sites, 7%) and no sites in Africa. Acari were the most studied taxonomic group
318 (33% of effect sizes), followed by Collembola (21%), Nematoda (7%) and Diplopoda (3%).
319 The remaining 31 taxonomic groups for which we found data make up 37% of our effect
320 sizes. The vast majority of effect sizes related to faunal abundance (329 effect sizes, 77%),
321 with relatively few effect sizes for the Shannon-Wiener index (48, 11%) and taxonomic
322 richness (53, 12%).

323 Most studies were experimental manipulations (87%) while there were relatively few
324 observational studies (13%). The majority of studies used spatial comparisons (85%), with
325 10% using temporal comparisons, and only 4% using both temporal and spatial
326 comparisons. Most effect sizes came from sampling carried out less than three years after

327 initial precipitation changes (60%) while 15% of effect sizes were from samples >10 years
328 after precipitation changes occurred. Following critical appraisal, only one study was
329 classified as having high validity, 16 had medium validity, and 16 had low validity. The major
330 reasons for studies failing to achieve high validity were a lack of randomisation of treatments
331 and risk of confounding variables. Samples were mainly taken during Autumn (132 effect
332 sizes, 31%) or Summer (92, 21%), with relatively few in Winter (55, 13%) and Spring (38,
333 9%).

334 **Impacts of precipitation change**

335 Precipitation reductions led to a 35% reduction in soil and litter fauna abundance (Figure 2a,
336 coefficient = -0.43, confidence intervals = -0.71, -0.17, p-value = 0.001, k = 185). There was
337 significant between-study heterogeneity ($Q = 2767$, p-value = <0.001) and the proportion of
338 this heterogeneity that was due between-study differences was high ($I^2 = 98\%$). Precipitation
339 increases led to a 39% increase in abundance in soil and litter fauna (Figure 2a, coefficient =
340 0.33, confidence intervals = 0.06, 0.59, p-value = 0.016, k = 139). Variation in effect size was
341 again significant ($Q = 1636$, p-value = <0.001) and a large amount of this was due to real
342 heterogeneity ($I^2 = 78$). For both precipitation reduction and increases, removing effect sizes
343 that failed Geary's test of normality did not qualitatively alter the results (Table S6). However,
344 in the case of precipitation reduction, removing studies with low validity markedly reduced
345 the summary effect size (Table S6). Further investigation revealed that this was likely to be
346 due to higher validity studies reducing precipitation in a more extreme manner.

347 The impacts of precipitation changes on both Shannon-Wiener diversity and
348 taxonomic richness were less pronounced than those seen for abundance. Shannon-Weiner
349 diversity showed significant reductions with both decreased precipitation (Figure 2b,
350 coefficient = -0.07, confidence intervals = -0.14, 0.00, p-value = 0.036, k = 33) and increased
351 precipitation (Figure 2b, coefficient = -0.08, confidence intervals = -0.14, -0.02, p-value =
352 0.005, k = 12). Precipitation reduction reduced taxonomic richness by 3%, but this effect was
353 not statistically significant (Figure 2c, coefficient = -0.03, confidence intervals = -0.10, 0.04,

354 p-value = 0.345, k = 35). Precipitation increase also reduced taxonomic richness, this time
355 by of 2%, but this effect was again not statistically significant (Figure 2c, coefficient = -0.02,
356 confidence intervals = -0.20, 0.17, p-value = 0.869, k = 15). Although most of these models
357 indicated significant variability in effect sizes, the proportion of heterogeneity due to
358 between-study differences was much lower than for the analyses of abundance ($I^2 = 0.68\%$,
359 Table S6). Removing effect sizes that failed Geary's test of normality did not qualitatively
360 alter the results but again removing studies with low validity tended to lead to more extreme
361 summary effect sizes (Table S6).

362

363 **Drivers of precipitation change impact**

364 When investigating the reasons for differences in the impact of precipitation changes
365 on abundance, the most parsimonious models included an interaction between the
366 magnitude of precipitation change and organism body size as well as moderators to account
367 for study size and whether effect sizes change over time (Table S7). Model-averaging
368 suggested that mesofauna abundance responded to changes in the magnitude of
369 precipitation, while this was not the case for microfauna and macrofauna (Figure 3). Of the
370 moderators only, the interaction between mesofauna and the magnitude of precipitation
371 change was statistically significant (coefficient = 0.005, SE = 0.002, p-value = 0.001), while
372 for microfauna and macrofauna the slopes were much less steep and not statistically
373 significant (Table S8). The most parsimonious models included the effects of study size and
374 publication year, suggesting that larger studies showed more positive impacts on abundance
375 and that the same was true for more recent studies (Figures S2 and S3, Table S8) but
376 neither effect was statistically significant. We tested whether the impact of precipitation
377 change differed between two of the most well-studied taxonomic groups, Collembola and
378 Acari (Table S9). While we found that both groups showed a response to changes in
379 precipitation magnitude, there was no statistically significant difference between the
380 responses (Figure S4, Table S10).

381 The most parsimonious models for changes in taxonomic richness included only the
382 magnitude of precipitation change or the year of publication (Table S11). Model-averaging
383 showed a significant positive relationship with precipitation change (coefficient = 0.002, SE =
384 0.001, p-value = 0.0473, Figure 4, Table S12), indicating support for the impact of
385 precipitation change magnitude. Again, more recent studies tended to have larger effect
386 sizes, although this trend was not statistically significant (Table S12). Similarly, for Shannon-
387 Wiener diversity the most parsimonious models included different combinations of the
388 magnitude of precipitation change and/or the year of publication (Table S13). Model
389 averaging showed a non-significant negative effect of precipitation magnitude on Shannon-
390 Wiener diversity (coefficient = -0.002, SE = 0.004, p-value = 0.703, Table S14), and small
391 non-statistically significant effects of study size and publication year (Figure S5).

392

393 **Study biases**

394 There are clear biases in the geographic distribution of studies, with a large number
395 of studies carried out in western Europe and the USA, but relatively few in South America
396 and Asia, and no studies found for Africa (Figure 5a). This translates to an
397 underrepresentation of tropical forest biomes, with most studies carried out in temperate
398 seasonal forests or woodland/shrubland biomes found in Mediterranean climates (Figure
399 5b). In addition to geographic biases, there were also a number of biases that could impact
400 the validity of study results. First, studies of the effects of precipitation reduction reduced
401 precipitation by 91% more than projected changes for the same location (Figure 6a,
402 coefficient = -2.37, SE = 0.65, p-value = 0.004), while studies of precipitation increase
403 increased precipitation by 58% more than projected changes, although this difference was
404 not statistically significant (Figure 6a, coefficient = 0.455, SE = 0.846, p-value = 0.603). For
405 more details of results for each of the 25 climate models used in this analysis see Figure S6.
406 Second, the plots used for experimental manipulations tended to be small for studies of
407 micro-, meso-, and macrofauna (Figure 6b), with median areas of 460 m², 300 m², and 36 m²
408 respectively.

409 **Discussion**

410 Our findings partially supported our hypothesis (H1), indicating that reductions in
411 precipitation generally cause large decreases in the abundance of soil and litter fauna in
412 forests, while precipitation increases have the opposite effect. However, impacts on
413 taxonomic richness and Shannon-Wiener diversity were typically less pronounced. Changes
414 in abundance depended on the magnitude of precipitation changes and taxa body size:
415 mesofauna abundance changes were positively correlated with changes in precipitation, but
416 there was little detectable effect of body size for either micro- or macrofauna. We found
417 weak support for a positive correlation between changes in precipitation and changes in
418 taxonomic richness but no support for this correlation for Shannon-Wiener diversity. Thus,
419 the best supported of our hypotheses regarding the variability in response to precipitation
420 changes was H5, that the impacts of precipitation change depended on taxa body size.
421 However, there was only weak support for H2, that increased magnitude of changes in
422 precipitation amplifies changes in abundance and diversity, and little support for the effects
423 of fauna occupying litter or soil (H3), possessing an exoskeleton (H4) or whether sites were
424 relatively humid or arid (H6) regarding the modification of impacts of precipitation changes.
425 Additionally, our analyses to account for publication biases relating to study size and
426 changes in effect sizes over time mean that these results are highly robust.

427 **Impacts of precipitation change**

428 Our results broadly agree with those of the meta-analysis by Peng et al. (2022), who found
429 that impacts of precipitation change on the abundance of soil fauna in forests were much
430 larger than for richness. However, our meta-analysis included more than three times as
431 many primary studies relating to forests, and over twice as many effect sizes, indicating that
432 our results represent an important advance in robustness. Our results also broadly mirrored
433 those found by the recent meta-analysis of Bristol et al. (2023) who focussed solely on
434 nematodes and showed a non-significant increase in abundance as a result of precipitation

435 increases and a non-significant decrease as a result of precipitation reductions. In addition,
436 unlike the synthesis of Goncharov et al. (2023) we found evidence for impacts of
437 precipitation change on mesofauna, while their study only found impacts of precipitation
438 change on nematodes. In contrast to all previous similar meta-analyses on this topic
439 (Blankinship et al., 2011; Goncharov et al., 2023; Peng et al., 2022), we found important
440 evidence for nuanced effects of precipitation change.

441 The lack of pronounced changes in either taxonomic richness or Shannon-Wiener
442 diversity was surprising, but one intriguing finding was that species richness changed little as
443 a result of precipitation change, while Shannon-Wiener diversity was significantly reduced.
444 This hints that, as suggested by others, some Oribatida and Collembola species become
445 increasingly dominant when soil moisture is altered, reducing evenness (Meehan et al.,
446 2020). In contrast with our findings for changes in abundance, we found relatively little
447 support for the effect of changes in precipitation magnitude or species traits on taxonomic
448 richness or Shannon-Wiener diversity. This could result from changes in local diversity as a
449 result of perturbations often not reflecting those in community composition (Hillebrand et al.,
450 2018; Zajicek et al., 2021). This occurs when there is turnover in the identity and abundance
451 of species but no systematic change in the number of species (Hillebrand et al., 2018) as
452 appears to be common for numerous human-impacted ecosystems (Dornelas et al., 2014;
453 Vellend et al., 2013). This response differs from that observed in soil microbial communities
454 under reduced precipitation, which not only show a reduced abundance of the active
455 community, but also lower diversity and markedly different composition (Metze et al., 2023;
456 Zhou et al., 2020). However, it is also possible that the apparent lack of effect is actually a
457 result of different responses to precipitation changes across taxonomic or functional groups
458 that we were unable to capture due to a lack of data.

459 **Drivers of precipitation change impact**

460 Our findings for changes in abundance suggest that water availability is a key
461 constraint for many forest soil taxa (Aupic-Samain, Baldy, et al., 2021), but that impacts of

462 soil moisture vary depending on organism body size. The effect of intense precipitation
463 changes on mesofauna abundance is consistent with previous studies that suggested that
464 this group can be particularly sensitive to environmental changes (Wu & Wang, 2019) and
465 that high-intensity disturbances can have an enduring effect on ecological processes and
466 hinder recovery (Nielsen & Ball, 2015). This could lead to reductions in the incorporation of
467 leaf litter into soil, given that litter forms a major part of the diet for taxa such as Collembola
468 and Oribatida (Potapov et al., 2022). The apparent lack of significant impact of precipitation
469 change on micro- and macrofauna, while contradicting our expectations, could have a
470 variety of causes.

471 Our results suggest that there is a hump-shaped relationship between the body size
472 of soil and litter fauna and their sensitivity to precipitation changes, with micro- and
473 macrofauna being relatively insensitive and mesofauna being highly sensitive. We
474 hypothesise that this sensitivity is caused by three factors. First, differences in the ability to
475 avoid predation. Under drier conditions, microfauna, such as nematodes, can become
476 restricted to small pores (Erktan et al., 2020) that act as refuges from predatory mesofauna
477 such as mites (Potapov et al., 2022) which are unable to access them. Mesofauna are
478 confined to larger, air-filled pores (Erktan et al., 2020). In contrast to nematodes, this
479 confinement does not protect them against predation, because meso- and macrofauna
480 predators can move between soil layers in search of prey (Potapov et al., 2022). Thus,
481 mesofauna remains subject to predation even in dry conditions.

482 Second, physical adaptations to dry conditions. Both micro- and macrofauna possess
483 physical adaptations which aid them in drier conditions. Microfauna, such as nematodes, can
484 go into anhydrobiosis when under drought stress (Landesman et al., 2011; Watanabe,
485 2006). Many macrofauna, such as spiders or millipedes, have thick exoskeletons which
486 protect them against desiccation as well as being highly mobile, thus allowing them to move
487 more easily to wetter soil patches. In contrast, many mesofauna, such as Collembola or
488 Protura, have few physical adaptations to drought conditions and have limited mobility within

489 the soil. As a consequence, they are likely subject to greater drought-induced mortality than
490 micro- or macrofauna.

491 Third, availability of food sources. Soil and litter fauna feed on a wide variety of food,
492 ranging from living or dead plant matter to soil bacteria and fungi, as well as other soil fauna
493 (Potapov et al., 2022). Changes in the biomass and palatability of these different food
494 sources as a result of precipitation reductions causes cascading bottom-up impacts
495 throughout soil food webs. While reductions in the food sources for all soil and litter fauna
496 seem likely in dry conditions, mesofauna may be more severely impacted than the other
497 groups. For example, many Collembola species are fungivores and drier conditions may
498 reduce the abundance and quality of fungi available to them. Drought conditions appear to
499 favour mycorrhizal fungi that contain melanin in their cell walls (Fernandez & Koide, 2014;
500 Pigott, 1982), making them resistant to decomposition thereby limiting food sources for
501 detritivores (Fernandez et al., 2013; Fernandez & Koide, 2014; Malik & Haider, 1982). In
502 addition, precipitation reductions can reduce saprotrophic fungi abundance, and important
503 source of food for Collembola (Sanders et al., 2024). However, many micro- and macrofauna
504 groups have relatively diverse diets, potentially providing a buffer when some sources of
505 food are scarce (Potapov et al., 2022). Similarly, reductions in precipitation can reduce litter
506 input, reducing the quantity of food for some detritivore mesofauna, and increase the carbon
507 content of litter (Deng et al., 2021), reducing decomposition rates, resulting in a shortage of
508 readily available nutrients for litter feeding fauna.

509 Under increased precipitation, the hump-shaped relationship between size and
510 abundance appears to be reversed. This implies that mesofauna is more sensitive to
511 increases in water resources than either micro- or macrofauna. Mesofauna appear to be
512 more easily affected by seasonal changes than macrofauna due to their smaller body size
513 and shorter life cycles (Wu & Wang, 2019), thus explaining their increase in abundance with
514 increased precipitation. Mesofauna may also be less affected by predation under wetter
515 conditions (Aupic-Samain, Baldy, et al., 2021). Meanwhile, for microfauna such as

516 nematodes, increased precipitation may reduce the overall fungal biomass, reducing
517 populations of fungivorous nematodes (Liu et al. 2020). At the same time some fungal
518 groups, such as saprotrophic fungi, on which mesofauna such as Collembola preferentially
519 feed, are expected to increase under wetter conditions (Sanders et al., 2024).

520 The effect of body size seen in our meta-analysis represents an advance in our
521 understanding of the responses of soil biota to changes in precipitation associated with
522 climate change. However, the mechanisms that regulate this response to changes in water
523 availability are currently unclear and further research could substantially improve our ability
524 to predict the future impact of climate change on the resilience of soils and their functioning
525 in the face of climate change. One such potential impact is that loss of mesofauna could
526 cause a reduction in the rate of litter decomposition (Song et al., 2020) resulting in a
527 reduction in the incorporation of organic matter into soils and a reduction in the complexity of
528 soil structure. Equally, such a reduction in soil mesofauna could lead to increases in the
529 abundance of taxa belonging to other size groups that also feed on litter (e.g. earthworms)
530 resulting in a change in the structure of soil food webs, which may potentially buffer the
531 impacts of precipitation changes on soil functioning. However, this replacement could entail
532 major changes in the physical structure of the soil, since earthworms are ecosystem
533 engineers which can alter soil porosity (Flores et al., 2021).

534 Although our explanations for the observed patterns are grounded in theory and
535 empirical evidence from the literature, new experiments and observations are needed to test
536 them. In particular, within broad taxonomic groups, there are large differences in key traits
537 that determine their response to precipitation change. For example, Collembola, vary in body
538 size, permeability of cuticle, and occupancy of different soil layers, all of which influence how
539 species respond to drought conditions (Ferrín et al., 2023). For Nematodes, body size and
540 trophic group are linked with fungivores and bacterivores being relatively small, and
541 omnivores and predators being relatively large (Sechi et al., 2018). Given these variations,
542 we urge researchers to identify soil and litter fauna to a higher taxonomic resolution, thus

543 allowing for more nuanced interpretations of how body size and other functional traits impact
544 responses to precipitation change.

545 **Study biases and recommendations for future research**

546 Our study identified a need for changes in studies of precipitation change impacts on
547 forest soil and litter fauna. The proposed changes may be difficult to implement, and we
548 acknowledge that decisions about study practicalities are the result of a mixture of factors
549 such as socioeconomics (Llorente-Culebras et al., 2023) and the obsession with academic
550 productivity (Fischer et al., 2012). First, linked to our finding that many experiments use
551 precipitation regime alterations that are much more extreme than projected future changes,
552 we advocate for researchers to clearly distinguish between experiments which aim to
553 simulate changes in mean annual precipitation and those that aim to simulate extreme
554 events such as droughts and extreme rainfall (Korell et al., 2020). Second, this study shows
555 that the scale of experimental manipulations in many studies may be too small to capture
556 changes in more mobile macrofauna taxa, and so larger-scale studies are needed that allow
557 for a wider range of organisms and processes to be studied (Hanson & Walker, 2020). Third,
558 we found strong geographic biases, with few studies found outside of temperate and
559 Mediterranean forest biomes, and thus suggest the greater need for studies outside of these
560 regions.

561 While there is a need for changes in how primary studies are conducted, the same is
562 true for syntheses relating to soil fauna. Our study represents one of most methodologically
563 robust meta-analyses to date in soil ecology, collating more studies on the impacts of
564 precipitation changes than previous similar meta-analyses (Blankinship et al., 2011; Peng et
565 al., 2022), despite our narrower focus on precipitation changes in forests, and thus providing
566 greater statistical power than previous efforts. We encourage more researchers to strive for
567 more robust evidence syntheses and familiarise themselves with existing guidance for
568 evidence synthesis in ecology (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence, 2018; Haddaway
569 et al., 2018; Figure S1, 2020). In our study we used the log response ratio as an effect size

570 metric, due to differences between studies in the units of abundance. Because the log
571 response ratio measures proportionate change in biodiversity relative to a control or baseline
572 value, there is a loss of information that can render meta-analyses vulnerable to possible
573 inferential errors when baselines vary across studies (Spake et al., 2023).

574 In addition, existing meta-analyses on the impacts of global change on soil fauna
575 (This study; Beaumelle et al., 2023; Blankinship et al., 2011; Bristol et al., 2023; Goncharov
576 et al., 2023; Peng et al., 2022; Phillips et al., 2023) use biodiversity metrics related to
577 abundance and alpha diversity, meaning we know little about impacts on more complex
578 aspects of biodiversity such as community composition and functional diversity. We
579 advocate for researchers to collate and use raw data from field studies to allow for more
580 nuanced 'full data' analyses which can avoid issues associated with the use of effect sizes
581 (Spake et al., 2023) and that are becoming the gold standard in other fields, such as
582 medicine (Culina et al., 2018; Spake et al., 2022). Finally, we recognise that we were unable
583 to explicitly examine the impact of study scale (e.g., grain, extent) on observed changes in
584 soil fauna biodiversity as a result of precipitation changes. However, given the general
585 importance of scale for observations in ecology (Spake et al., 2021) and the findings that
586 precipitation change experiments have scale-dependent effects on other taxa (Korell et al.,
587 2021) we encourage researchers to address this topic in future syntheses.

588 We acknowledge that our meta-analysis focussed solely on the impacts of
589 precipitation changes and ignored the potential impacts of other drivers that could have
590 synergistic impacts on soil and litter fauna. In the real world, ecosystems are typically
591 affected by more than one of global change factor (e.g. temperature increases, nitrogen
592 deposition) at any given time (Bowler et al., 2020). Importantly, interactions between
593 different global change factors can cause unpredictable changes in soil biodiversity and
594 functioning (Eisenhauer et al., 2012; Rillig et al., 2019). In the case of precipitation
595 reductions there is a clear synergy with temperature increases as these can lead to
596 increased evapotranspiration and further reductions in soil moisture. Such conditions could

597 further stress soil fauna sensitive to changes in moisture by limiting their diets (Sanders et
598 al., 2024) or directly causing desiccation. However, the recent meta-analysis of Peng et al.
599 (2022) suggests there are currently few primary studies that have investigated this synergy,
600 especially in forests. We urge researchers to prioritise experiments investigating the impacts
601 of multiple global change factors to inform more realistic predictions of future change.

602

603 **Conclusion**

604 Overall, our results suggest that forest soil and litter fauna abundance is sensitive to
605 changes in precipitation, and that for mesofauna this impact depends on the magnitude of
606 precipitation change. Meanwhile, alpha diversity appeared to be relatively insensitive, with
607 little evidence that changes were related to the magnitude of precipitation change. Given soil
608 mesofauna affect soil functions, such as litter decomposition, changes in the abundance of
609 this group may result in changes in the soil physical structure, soil nutrients, and soil carbon.
610 In turn, changes in mesofauna abundance will also alter the trophic structure of belowground
611 food webs. Our results provide new insights into belowground biodiversity change in forests
612 that can inform more realistic soil models in the future (Deckmyn et al., 2020; Flores et al.,
613 2021). In addition, we call on global change researchers to conduct more realistic studies of
614 changes in mean annual precipitation, droughts, and extreme precipitation in future, in line
615 with representative concentration pathways (RCPs; van Vuuren et al., 2011) as well as
616 larger scale experiments to capture impacts on soil fauna more fully.

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643

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Table 1 - Different PECOS elements used to define the scope of the meta-analysis

PECOS element	Description
Population	Soil and litter fauna found in forest ecosystems. We defined these as invertebrates which spend a significant proportion of their life in litter and/or soil, excluding ants. Details of the selected taxonomic groups are in Table S1.
Exposure	Reductions and increases in precipitation.
Comparison	Any comparison between forests that vary in the frequency or intensity of precipitation that they are subject to. This comparison may be spatial or temporal.
Outcomes	Abundance, biomass, and diversity of soil and litter fauna.
Space	Studies carried out in the field. All types of forest and woodland are considered relevant.

1225

1226

1227 **Figure 1** - Conceptual diagram of the hypotheses we test in this study - (a) precipitation

1228 reductions negatively affect soil fauna abundance and diversity, while precipitation increases

1229 have positive impacts; (b) abundance and diversity changes with respect to control plots are
 1230 driven by the magnitude of precipitation changes; (c) the effects of changes in precipitation
 1231 depend on whether invertebrate fauna are found in the soil or the litter; (d) the effects of
 1232 changes in precipitation depend on whether invertebrate fauna have an exoskeleton or not;
 1233 (e) the effects of changes in precipitation depend on the body size of invertebrate fauna; (f)
 1234 the effects of changes in precipitation depend on the aridity of the forest ecosystem. Dashed
 1235 lines represent points at which there is no change in precipitation or no change in effect
 1236 sizes relating to soil and litter fauna biodiversity. Effect size refers to the differences in
 1237 abundance or biodiversity between control and treatment groups, with positive changes
 1238 representing increases in abundance or biodiversity and decreases representing a loss in
 1239 abundance or biodiversity. For all of these hypotheses we assume that abundance and
 1240 diversity did not change for the control groups.

1241

1242 **Figure 2** - Changes in the (a) abundance (b) Shannon-Wiener diversity index, and (c)
 1243 taxonomic richness of soil and litter fauna in forests as a result of precipitation change. Large
 1244 points refer to the summary effect size, thicker bars around them representing the 95%
 1245 confidence intervals, and the thinner bars the 95% prediction intervals. Smaller, semi-
 1246 transparent points represent individual comparisons. Differences in their size refer to the
 1247 weight they supply to each analysis. The vertical dashed line represents where the effect
 1248 size is equal to zero (i.e. where there is no difference between control and treatment
 1249 groups). Annotations on the left of the plot refer to the number of comparisons in each
 1250 analysis (k) and, in parentheses, the number of studies they are taken from. Annotations on
 1251 the right of the plot refer to the mean weighted percentage change for each analysis and
 1252 asterisks (*) indicate when effect sizes are significantly different from zero.

1253
 1254 **Figure 3** - Changes in the abundance of soil and litter fauna in forests relative to changes in
 1255 precipitation for different faunal size classes. Points represent individual comparisons with
 1256 different point sizes representing the different weights of comparisons to the analysis. Solid
 1257 lines represent predictions from the most parsimonious model ($R^2=0.13$), with darker
 1258 coloured bands representing the 95% confidence intervals, and the lighter bands the 95%
 1259 prediction intervals. Dashed lines represent points at which there is no change in
 1260 precipitation (x equal to zero) or in effect size (y equal to zero). Annotations on the plot refer
 1261 to the number of comparisons in each analysis (k) and, in parentheses, the number of
 1262 studies they are taken from.

1263

1264 **Figure 4** - Changes in taxonomic richness relative to changes in precipitation. Points
 1265 represent individual comparisons with different point sizes representing the different weights
 1266 of points in the analysis. The solid line represents predictions from the most parsimonious
 1267 model ($R^2=0.26$), with darker coloured bands representing the 95% confidence intervals, and
 1268 the lighter bands the 95% prediction intervals. Dashed lines represent points at which the x
 1269 and y axes are equal to zero. Annotations on the plot refer to the number of comparisons in
 1270 the analysis (k) and, in parentheses, the number of studies they are taken from.

(a)

(b)

1271

1272 **Figure 5** - (a) The location of study sites and (b) distribution within biomes. Studies of
 1273 precipitation increase are shown by blue upward-pointing triangle symbols, studies of
 1274 precipitation decrease by red downward-pointing triangles, and studies that investigated both
 1275 increases and decreases are shown by purple diamonds. The size of the symbols indicates
 1276 the number of comparisons made at each location (minimum: 1, maximum: 88). In (b) the
 1277 location of each site in a Whittaker biome diagram is defined by mean annual temperature and
 1278 mean annual precipitation. Map lines delineate study areas and do not necessarily depict
 1279 accepted national boundaries

1280
 1281 **Figure 6** - Biases that affect the validity of study results: (a) Differences in precipitation
 1282 changes investigated in studies compared to projected precipitation changes based on 25
 1283 climate model projections for 2041-2060; (b) Sizes of plots used in experimental studies of
 1284 precipitation changes effects on the differing body size groups of invertebrate soil and litter
 1285 fauna. In (a) points represent median values for each group and error bars the 95%
 1286 confidence intervals. The dashed vertical line represents the point at which there is no
 1287 difference between projected and studied level of precipitation change. Annotations on the
 1288 right of the plot refer to the mean percentage change for each analysis and asterisks (*)
 1289 indicate when effect sizes are significantly different from zero.

1290